

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Optimal Control of Arrival Rates in a Queueing Model with Stochastic and Time Dependent Demand

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Abstract

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Objectives: Examining a queueing model for production and service systems with stochastic and time-dependent demand is the aim of this research. In order to maximize the system's net benefit while preserving dependable and efficient system performance, the major objective is to optimize throughput revenue, backlog expenses, and arrival rate control costs. **Methods:** An optimization framework for assessing performance over time is developed using an $M/M/1$ queueing model in conjunction with the Piecewise-Stationary Approach (PSA). The objective function is formulated using three key components: the backlog penalty cost, the expected throughput income, and the cost of dynamically changing arrival rates. The goal of the model is to maintain analytical simplicity while capturing time-varying demand behavior. **Finding:** In time-dependent and stochastic situations, the proposed approach offers a useful framework for managing arrival rates. It is appropriate for MTO production and service systems with varying demand since it promotes better operational decision-making by striking a balance between system utilization and service efficiency. **Novelty:** This study allows time-dependent queue performance evaluation with flexible computing complexity by merging an arrival-rate control optimization framework with the Piecewise-Stationary Approach (PSA).

Keywords: $M/M/1$ queueing model; Optimization; MTO (Make-to-order) manufacturing system; Piecewise-Stationary Approach (PSA)

1 Introduction

In service and make-to-order production settings, queueing systems frequently function with demand that fluctuates. Managing congestion, maintaining service standards, and improving system performance can all be performed by modifying arrival rates. In this work, we propose an optimization model that optimizes a queueing system's overall performance by concentrating on three crucial factors: throughput income, backlog expenses resulting from unfulfilled demand, and arrival rate adjustment costs. The simplicity of using three main parameters enables efficient optimization provides insight into core system dynamics and makes the model broadly applicable.

Make-to-order (MTO) systems are widely used in industries such as computing, automotive and food production^{(1), (2)}. Unlike make-to-stock systems, MTO production starts only after receiving customer orders, making it challenging to manage demand variability. Instead of relying on inventory management, strategies like mass customization⁽³⁾, customer-centric⁽⁴⁾, capacity management^{(5), (6)} or revenue management⁽⁷⁾ are often employed.

Stolletz⁽⁸⁾ explored the optimization of queueing systems with parameters that change over time, such as arrival rates, service capacities, or queue configurations. There are various approaches to optimizing time-dependent queueing systems, with many relying on heuristic techniques. These methods can generally be classified into several main categories each with unique methodologies and challenges.

Recently, a lot of research has been done on optimal control in queueing systems. In order to reduce congestion while taking control costs into account, Lefebvre and Yaghoubi⁽⁹⁾ examined an $M/M/k$ queueing system in which the number of active servers can be dynamically controlled.

In order to improve performance analysis for correlated stochastic systems, Wang and Hu⁽¹⁰⁾ created a computationally efficient recursive technique to evaluate waiting time moments and inter-departure features in queueing systems with correlated inter-arrival and service durations.

Analytical price expansions under intricate stochastic volatility and jump processes were created by Qiao *et al.*⁽¹¹⁾ facilitating effective model calibration and enhancing computational viability in financial optimization issues. A finite-buffer Markovian queue with demand-driven discharge was examined by Ilieva and Ayhan⁽¹²⁾ where clients might be evacuated early when the system reaches capacity. To ascertain which client class should be let go in order to optimize long-term profit, they created ideal policies. In order to derive steady-state probabilities and performance metrics like average system size and expected waiting time, Therasal and Thiagarajan⁽¹³⁾ proposed a finite capacity interdependent queueing model with Poisson arrivals, exponential service, server breakdown, and controllable arrival rates. Nasrallah *et al.*⁽¹⁴⁾ created a Markovian queueing model that incorporates scheduled arrival patterns in order to more accurately depict variations in passenger demand in public transit systems in the real world. In order to assess congestion levels, optimize service intervals and enhance capacity management, their approach combines simulation methods with Markovian equations. Incorporating scheduled arrival dynamics into urban transport operations improves system responsiveness and facilitates more efficient scheduling and resource allocation decisions. A modified Min (N, D)-control method was proposed by Luo *et al.*⁽¹⁵⁾ for an $M/M/1$ queue with delayed randomized repeated vacations. Stochastic decomposition was used to derive steady-state queue length distributions. Using probability generating functions and renewal reward theory, the authors obtained explicit formulations for expected queue length and long-run cost. They then demonstrated that the modified policy offers better cost efficiency when compared to conventional N-policy and D-policy control procedures. Fluid, piecewise-stationary approach (PSA) and stationary backlog-carryover models were used by Vogel and Stolletz⁽¹⁶⁾ to study capacity planning in MTO systems. According to their findings, whereas stochastic interdependencies reflected by backlog-carryover models might result in anticipatory capacity modifications like inverse capacity boost, PSA calculates capacity periodwise without taking future demand changes into account. Ahmadi *et al.*⁽¹⁷⁾ used commitment lead time to study optimum control policies for manufacturing-to-order systems preorder techniques that provide advance demand information which has a considerable impact on the best choices for production and stock management. Optimal production control in a time-varying double-ended queueing model with nonstationary stochastic demand was examined by Lee *et al.*⁽¹⁸⁾. Gross *et al.*⁽¹⁹⁾ established steady-state equations and used specific models to illustrate them. A retrial queueing–inventory system with regulated arrivals, server disruptions, and emergency vacations was examined by Nithya *et al.*⁽²⁰⁾. Their analysis of system performance demonstrates that appropriate server control and arrival may greatly increase system efficiency.

In some real-world systems, service rate adjustments may not be feasible due to cost constraints, resource limitations, or physical constraints. For instance, in manufacturing environments with fixed equipment capacities, service rate changes may require significant investments in new machinery or workforce, which is not always practical. Alternatively, customer service centers may have fixed staffing levels during specific periods, making it challenging to increase service rate on short notice.

The goal of this new study is for optimum queue performance by controlling the arrival rate with the the step-function service (or production) rate constant during subintervals. This approach is unique because queue optimization frequently adjusts both arrival and service rates to balance capacity and demand. The service rate's step function shows that the system's capacity fluctuates in distinct stages, like hourly or daily shifts, which reflect periods when the service rate is constant but may change at specific times. The novelty lies in adjusting the arrival rate to satisfy this stepped service rate rather than adjusting the service rate itself, which is set in steps.

2 Methodology

2.1 Problem Description and Model Formulation:

In this current study, the objective function provided aims to maximize net benefit, Z, for a manufacturing system that operates over a planning horizon $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ where each period has a length l and represent one or several weeks or days. In this setup, the manufacturer's objective function has three main components:

1. **Revenue from Finished Goods:** The revenue is generated based on the throughput (i.e., the number of units completed and ready for sale) in each period. The throughput $E(Th_i)$ represents the expected number of units completed in the i^{th} period. Revenue per unit is denoted by r , so the revenue contribution to the objective is $rE(Th_i)$ for each period.
2. **Cost for the Backlog of Orders:** Backlog costs represent the holding costs of pending or unfulfilled orders, which can include penalties for delays, storage costs, or costs due to reduced customer satisfaction. The backlog cost per unit in period is represented by h , and $E(L_i)$ represents the expected backlog (number of pending orders) in that period. This component is given by $-hE(L_i)$ as it reduces net profit.
3. **Cost associated with managing arrival rates:** Since the manufacturing system can dynamically adjust arrival rates i.e., manage incoming orders to minimize waiting time and reduce waiting cost. However, there are still costs associated with managing arrival rates. The term $-s(\lambda_i - \lambda_i^*)$ minimizes unnecessary reductions in arrival rates, where

- (a) s is the cost per adjusted unit of arrival rate
- (b) λ_i is the actual arrival rate in period l
- (c) λ_i^* is a reduced or target arrival rate, representing an optimal rate that balances demand with capacity to minimize waiting time and reduce waiting cost

$$MaxZ = l \sum_{i=1}^n (rE(Th_i) - hE(L_i) - s(\lambda_i - \lambda_i^*)) \tag{1}$$

2.2 Goal of Objective Function

The purpose of this function is to:

1. **Maximize Throughput Revenue:** By maximizing $r.E[Th_i]$ the manufacturer aims to process as many orders as possible within each period, thus maximizing revenue.
2. **Minimize Backlog Costs:** The term $-h.E[L_i]$ minimizes the backlog to avoid excess holding costs, ensuring orders are processed promptly.
3. **Control Arrival Rate Reductions:** The term $-s(\lambda_i - \lambda_i^*)$ minimizes unnecessary reductions in arrival rates, balancing demand with capacity.

2.3 Optimization Arrival Rate for the Piecewise Stationary Approximation

This section presents the analytical result on an optimal value of arrival rate in each period l . For the piecewise stationary approximation according to objective function (1), this approach applies stationary result in each period independently. The stationary performance measure of interest for a $AM/M/1$ queue are $E(Th_i) = \lambda_i^*$, $E(L_i) = \frac{\lambda_i^*}{\mu_i - \lambda_i^*}$ (19), thus the objective function (1) becomes

$$MaxZ = l \sum_{i=1}^n (r \lambda_i^* - h \frac{\lambda_i^*}{\mu_i - \lambda_i^*} - s(\lambda_i - \lambda_i^*)) \tag{2}$$

Theorem 1: The optimal arrival rates of the piecewise-stationary approach are

$$\lambda_i^* = \min \left\{ \mu_i - \sqrt{\frac{h\mu_i}{r+s}}, \lambda_i \right\} \tag{3}$$

Proof: Consider any period $i = 1, \dots, n$. setting the first order derivative of objective function Z with respect to the reduced arrival rate λ_i^* equals to zero result in

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \lambda_i^*} = r - \frac{h(\mu_i - \lambda_i^*) + \lambda_i^*}{(\mu_i - \lambda_i^*)^2} + s$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \lambda_i^*} = r + s - h \frac{\mu_i}{(\mu_i - \lambda_i^*)^2}$$

$$r + s - h \frac{\mu_i}{(\mu_i - \lambda_i^*)^2} = 0$$

$$\lambda_i^* = \mu_i \pm \sqrt{\frac{h\mu_i}{r+s}}$$

The Hessian matrix is,

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial \lambda_i^* \partial \lambda_j^*} = \begin{cases} \frac{-2lh\mu_i}{(\mu_i - \lambda_i^*)^3} & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases} \in R^{n \times n}$$

is negative definite because all element on the diagonal are negative when $\lambda_i^* = \mu_i - \sqrt{\frac{h\mu_i}{r+s}}$ and all other equal zero. Thus, Z is concave.

By 2nd derivative test is clarify that optimal value is $\lambda_i^* = \mu_i - \sqrt{\frac{h\mu_i}{r+s}}$ for maximizing equation (2). If $\lambda_i^* > \lambda_i$, then the objective function is maximized at λ_i .

The optimal piecewise-stationary arrival rates λ_i^* described in equation (3) is monotonically increasing in μ_i , monotonically increasing in h, and monotonically decreasing in r and s.

3 Result and Discussion

In this work, by dynamically modifying the arrival rate, the proposed optimization framework, when combined with the Piecewise-Stationary Approach (PSA) can maintain higher service utilization during periods of low demand and avoid excessive congestion during periods of peak demand. In service sectors with variable demand management and Make-to-Order (MTO) production systems, this leads to a reduction in backlog accumulation and an increase in net benefit. In the literature⁽¹⁶⁾, the manufacture’s objective function consist of three parts (i) revenue for finished goods (ii) cost for the backlog of order (iii) and cost for additional production capacity. But if we not change in production capacity then we manage arrival rate to get maximum profit and reduced waiting time or waiting cost.

This technique performs better than conventional methods in time-dependent queueing settings where the service rate is fixed and uncontrollable. Due to its ability to dynamically modify arrival rates interval-wise rather than depend on steady-state conditions, it is particularly useful in situations where demand varies over time. Throughput revenue, arrival rate adjustment cost and backlog cost are all concurrently balanced by the framework’s structured optimization-based mechanism. Not only does it capture time-varying behavior, but it is computationally simpler than fully dynamic stochastic control methods. More realistic and feasible policies are provided in systems such as seasonal service demand or make-to-order production. Additionally, it is beneficial when industries have the ability to affect arrivals through scheduling, pricing, or invitation-based systems.

3.1 Numerical Experiments

A set of parameters $r = 2$, $h = 0.5$ and $s = 1$ are chosen to calculate the adjusted arrival rate λ_i^* . These parameters are used to modify the arrival rate by adjusting it based on the service rate μ_i .

Table1:

Table 1. Different values of λ_i and μ_i in different period.

Period	Arrival Rate (λ_i)	Service Rate (μ_i)
1 – 15	2.9	3
16 – 30	3.5	5
31 – 45	1.5	2
46 – 60	3.0	4

1. Computation for λ_i^*

The adjusted arrival rate λ_i^* is calculated using the formula:

$$\lambda_i^* = \min \left\{ \mu_i - \sqrt{\frac{h\mu_i}{r+s}}, \lambda_i \right\}$$

This formula adjusts the arrival rate in response to the system’s service capacity and the specified parameters. The minimum function ensures that the adjusted arrival rate does not exceed the original arrival rate.

2. Visualization

The results are plotted to visualize the adjusted arrival rate λ_i^* over time, with different periods of the system. The plot helps to understand the dynamic behavior of the system as it responds to varying arrival rates and service rates.

Fig 1. Optimized arrival rate as per the parameters.

A numerical research with time-dependent arrival and service rates was carried out across 60 periods. There were four demand stages in the system’s operation. Between periods 1 and 15, the service rate was 3 and the arrival rate was 2.9. Arrivals increased to 3.5 over periods 16–30, while service capacity increased to 5. With a service rate of 2, demand fell to 1.5 over periods 31–45. Service and arrival levels stopped off at 4 and 3, respectively, over periods 46–60.

In Figure 1, arrivals decreased from 2.9 to about 2.29 (a reduction of about 21%) throughout periods 1–15. From 16 to 30, there is no decrease ($\lambda = 3.5 < \text{capacity threshold} \approx 4.09$). Arrivals were lowered from 1.5 to 1.42 (a 5% decrease) throughout

periods 31–45. No decrease ($\lambda = 3 < \text{threshold} \approx 3.18$) for periods 46–60. The arrival rate was only aggressively lowered when it was nearly at system capacity. Figure 1 shows how the arrival rate per period is adjusted to maximize objective function.

These findings show that the control strategy is selective, permitting full demand utilization when there is adequate service capacity and lowering arrivals only when there is a substantial danger of congestion. Despite its advantages, the proposed method has drawbacks. If demand varies significantly or exhibits very variable patterns, the accuracy of this estimate may be reduced.

4 Conclusion

The primary contribution is optimizing throughput revenue, arrival adjustment expenses, and backlog costs all at the same time while maintaining a steady service rate. During moments of high demand, numerical data indicated that the ideal circumstance arrival rate dropped by about 21% (from 2.9 to 2.29),

preventing congestion while maintaining throughput. In circumstances where operational or financial constraints restrict modifying service capacity, this approach is more practical than service control techniques. The restrictions include assumptions about exponential distribution. Future studies ought to concentrate on broad distribution models that make use of multi-server situations and real-time demand data. When demand control is more feasible than service adjustment, this strategy works well in transportation terminals, logistical hubs, customized manufacturing, fixed-quantity manufacturing processes and service hubs.

5 Conflict of interest

Not applicable

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